

1 **System-based reliability analysis of stainless steel frames under gravity loads**

2 Itsaso Arrayago^{a*}, Kim J.R. Rasmussen^b

3 ^a *Dept. of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Spain*

4 ^b *School of Civil Engineering, The University of Sydney, Australia*

5 * Corresponding author: Itsaso Arrayago, Jordi Girona 1-3, Building C1, 08034 Barcelona, Spain,
6 itsaso.arrayago@upc.edu

7 **ABSTRACT**

8 Current structural codes for steel and stainless steel structures such as AISC 360-16, AISC 370-21,
9 AS/NZS 4100 and Eurocode 3 are based on the traditional *two-step* member-based design approach, in
10 which internal actions are first obtained from a structural analysis, usually elastic, and the strength of each
11 member and connection is subsequently checked using a structural design standard. However, the most
12 recent versions of these standards already incorporate preliminary versions of the direct, or *one-step*,
13 system-based design alternative, which is based on the *design-by-analysis* concept and allows evaluating
14 the strength of structures directly from numerical simulations, although the standards in their current form
15 do not provide reliability requirements for structural systems. Therefore, it is necessary to build a rigorous
16 structural reliability framework to investigate acceptable target reliability indices for structural systems
17 and to provide adequate system safety factors and system resistance factors. While this framework has
18 been developed based on advanced Finite Element analysis for hot-rolled and cold-formed carbon steel
19 structures in recent years in the form of the Direct Design Method (DDM), the framework does not exist
20 for stainless steel structures. This paper presents an extension of the DDM to the analysis of stainless steel
21 structures, in which system reliability calibrations are presented for six stainless steel portal frames under
22 gravity loads covering the three most common stainless steel families and different failure modes using
23 advanced numerical simulations. From the derived reliability calibrations, suitable system safety factors
24 $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s are proposed for the direct design of stainless steel frames in the
25 European, US and Australian design frameworks under gravity loads.

26 **KEYWORDS**

27 advanced analysis; probability-based design; reliability calibrations; stainless steel structures; structural
28 reliability

29 HIGHLIGHTS

- 30 • Extension of the Direct Design Method to stainless steel structures is presented.
- 31 • Rigorous reliability framework is built and presented for the analysis of stainless steel structures
32 under gravity loads.
- 33 • Six cold-formed stainless steel portal frames are analysed, including different stainless steel
34 families and failure modes.
- 35 • System reliability calibrations are presented for the Eurocode, US and Australian design
36 frameworks, covering different live-to-dead load ratios.
- 37 • System safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_S are proposed for the target reliability
38 indices typically adopted in national design frameworks.

39 1. INTRODUCTION

40 The most commonly accepted approach for determining structural reliability, i.e. the probability of
41 failure of a system of structural members, is to assess the reliability of a structural system by requiring
42 the probability of loads Q exceeding the structural resistance R (or reaching a certain limit state more
43 generally) to be less than an adopted target value, in which models for resistance and loading are
44 individually defined. Current design of structures is based on traditional limit state criteria following a
45 *two-step* approach where internal actions are first determined from a structural analysis, usually elastic,
46 and limit states are subsequently checked for members and connections such that the ultimate capacity
47 of the structure is reached when the first member or connection reaches its ultimate limit state.
48 Provisions for these checks are given by structural codes for the particular materials, e.g. steel [1-4], in
49 which design parameters and their random variations are modelled by nominal or characteristic values
50 based on partial coefficient methods. However, the exponential growth of the computational power of
51 standard desktop computers and rapid advances in design software during the past decades have made
52 it possible to accurately predict the behaviour and failure of complex structural systems, providing
53 engineers with the opportunity to progress from the current *two-step* member-based design method to a
54 direct system-based *design-by-analysis* approach. One of these system-based methods is the Direct
55 Design Method (DDM), which is based on a geometric and material nonlinear (advanced) analysis that

56 incorporates effects known to substantially affect the behaviour and strength of systems, like residual
 57 stresses and geometric imperfections. Typically, the analysis is performed using the Finite Element
 58 Method. With the DDM, the strength of structures can be directly evaluated from numerical simulations,
 59 eliminating the need for subsequently checking member and connection resistances. The DDM ensures
 60 a more uniform reliability of the complete structure across a range of structural systems [5], can be
 61 applied equally to simple and complex geometries, and as such encourages innovation, and has the
 62 potential to lead to lighter and more economical designs [6-9].

63 A few structural codes for carbon steel (AS/NZS 4100 [3], AISC 360-16 [4]) and stainless steel
 64 (AISC 370-21 [10]) already incorporate provisions for analysis-based design, but do not provide
 65 adequate reliability requirements for structural systems. In this context, a new part of Eurocode 3 is
 66 being developed for steel structures, *Part 1-14: Design assisted by finite element analysis* [11], which
 67 will include provisions for how to create finite element models to be used in design. The design
 68 equations in these cases are given by Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 for the Eurocode and the US/Australian design
 69 frameworks, respectively, where R_k and R_n are the characteristic and nominal resistances of the system,
 70 respectively, Q_{ki} and Q_{ni} denote the characteristic and nominal structural loads, respectively, γ_i is the
 71 corresponding load factor and finally, $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s are the safety factor and the resistance factor of the
 72 system, respectively.

$$\frac{R_k}{\gamma_{M,s}} \geq \sum \gamma_i Q_{ki} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\phi_s R_n \geq \sum \gamma_i Q_{ni} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

73 Although the abovementioned standards require that “a comparable or higher level of reliability” than
 74 existing member-based provisions be achieved when designing by analysis, they do not include
 75 provisions or guidance on acceptable target reliability indices β_0 for structural systems, nor do they
 76 provide system-based safety factors or give guidance on how to determine these. Thus, a framework for
 77 determining appropriate system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ or system resistance factors ϕ_s based on rigorous
 78 structural reliability considerations is fundamental for the variety of structural types and materials
 79 covered by these design codes. In recent years, design recommendations have been proposed for hot-
 80

81 rolled carbon steel frames [6,7], cold-formed steel frames [8,9], steel storage rack frames [12] and steel
82 scaffolds [13] in the framework of the Direct Design Method. However, such reliability analysis
83 framework does not exist for stainless steel structures. This is being addressed in the NewGeneSS
84 project [14], which is developing the basis of the DDM design method for stainless steel structures.

85 With significant strain-hardening properties, high mean-to-nominal resistance ratios (overstrength
86 ratios) and noticeable nonlinear stress-strain response, stainless steel structures require independent
87 reliability calibrations [15-18]. While these are structures with potentially higher resistance reserve due
88 to strain-hardening and high overstrength ratios, the material nonlinearities can also cause premature
89 stiffness losses that can increase deflections and further amplify second-order effects [18,19]. This is
90 apparent in international design standards, which provide different design equations and safety factors
91 (or resistance factors) for equivalent design situations for stainless steel and carbon steel members, with
92 the factors for stainless steel structural members being generally more conservative. The Eurocode
93 Standard for stainless steel structures prEN 1993-1-4 [2] has traditionally recommended a partial safety
94 factor of $\gamma_M = 1.10$ for cross-section and member resistances, while the γ_M value recommended for
95 carbon steel in prEN 1993-1-1 [1] is 1.00, although different values may be specified in the different
96 National Annexes. The difference in the recommended partial safety factors can be attributed partly to
97 the considerably more extensive pool of data available for carbon steel structures and partly to the lower
98 variability exhibited by structural steels in terms of material properties. Conversely, the upcoming
99 versions of the AISC 370-21 [10] and ASCE 8 [20] specifications adopt a resistance factor of $\phi = 0.90$
100 for the design of stainless steel members, which is equivalent to a safety factor of about $1/0.90 = 1.11$
101 and equal to the resistance factors prescribed for carbon steel structural members in AISC 360-16 [4]
102 and AISI S100-16 [21]. Nevertheless, the superseded ASCE 8 specification adopted a resistance factor
103 of $\phi = 0.85$ (equivalent to safety factors of $1/0.85 = 1.18$) in its 2002 version. Finally, while the
104 Australian AS/NZS 4100 [3] Specification requires a resistance factor of $\phi = 0.90$ to be adopted for
105 carbon steel members, the current AS/NZS 4673 [22] Specification uses the value of $\phi = 0.85$ for the
106 design of cold-formed stainless steel cross-sections and members.

107 This paper presents the derivation of appropriate system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and resistance factors
108 ϕ_s to adopt in the design-by-advanced analysis of stainless steel cold-formed portal frames subjected
109 to gravity load combinations. Section 2 describes the characteristics of the nominal frames considered
110 in the analysis, while in Section 3, Finite Element (FE) models developed for both nominal frames and
111 subsequent simulation studies are described, including the validation of the FE model. In Section 4, the
112 full reliability analysis framework for stainless steel frames is described, covering the probabilistic
113 models for the different random variables considered and the system reliability assessment. Finally, the
114 reliability calibration results are presented and discussed in Section 5, and suitable system safety factors
115 $\gamma_{M,S}$ and resistance factors ϕ_s are proposed for the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks
116 investigated.

117 **2. SYSTEM STRENGTH OF STAINLESS STEEL FRAMES**

118 2.1. DESCRIPTION OF NOMINAL FRAMES

119 This study considers single-storey, single-bay stainless steel portal frames of the type shown in Figure
120 1. Such portal frames are typically found in industrial settings and comprise the great majority of steel
121 buildings constructed [23]. The study on stainless steel frames presented in this paper is based on six
122 different frames, for which the typical nominal dimensions for the overall layout were chosen to
123 reproduce frame geometries commonly used in practise [24]. The portal frames are assumed to be
124 connected through five uniformly distributed longitudinal purlins along the rafters and longitudinal
125 bracings at the mid-height of the columns, as shown in Figure 1, as well as a wind bracing system in
126 the roof planes and the vertical walls. All portal frames comprised members made from cold-formed
127 rectangular hollow section (RHS) tubes, with the same section geometries for columns and rafters. The
128 six frames covered the three most common stainless steel families: while for Frames 1 and 2 the
129 common austenitic stainless steel grade EN 1.4301 (ASTM 304) was chosen, Frames 3 and 4
130 correspond to the typical duplex grade EN 1.4462 (ASTM 2205) and Frames 5 and 6 represent the
131 ferritic grade EN 1.4003 (ASTM UNS S40977).

132 The nominal overall frame geometries (span length s , heights at the eaves H_1 and at the roof ridge
133 H_2) and cross-section definitions (cross-section height H , width B and thickness t) for each frame are

134 summarized in Table 1, and were selected to produce a variety of failure modes, as discussed in Section
135 2.2. Note that Frames 1, 3 and 5 have the same overall frame and cross-section definition but correspond
136 to different stainless steel families to illustrate the effect of the material in system reliability
137 calculations. The definitions of initial imperfections, connection stiffness, material properties and
138 residual stresses adopted in the nominal stainless steel portal frames investigated in this paper are based
139 on relevant standards and the literature, and are described in detail in the following sections.

140 *2.1.1. Initial geometric imperfections*

141 Initial geometric imperfections relevant to cold-formed stainless steel frames include frame out-of-
142 plumbness imperfections, member out-of-straightness imperfections and local cross-sectional
143 imperfections. These three types of initial imperfections can influence the strength and stiffness of
144 stainless steel frames, although frame and member imperfections generally cause the most significant
145 reductions in failure loads of the tubular type of members considered in this paper. Consequently,
146 relevant international design standards include clauses providing design values for these initial
147 geometric imperfections and requirements on how to include them in numerical simulations, with small
148 differences among the standards. When determining the strength of the nominal frames, the most critical
149 combination of the different directions of each geometric imperfection type (i.e. combination resulting
150 in the lowest frame strength) was determined and adopted for the nominal structural models. In
151 determining frame imperfections in the Eurocode design framework, prEN 1993-1-14 [11] refers to
152 prEN 1993-1-1 [1], which defines a design (or nominal) value of the basic out-of-plumbness angle ϕ of
153 $1/200$, and adopts a nominal member out-of-straightness imperfection with a shape derived from the
154 relevant elastic buckling mode and an amplitude e_0 of $L/1000$ when local imperfections are combined
155 with member imperfections, where L is the length of the member. Alternatively, AS/NZS 4100 [3],
156 AISC 360-16 [4] and AISC 370-21 [10] specify a slightly lower out-of-plumbness angle ϕ of $1/500$ for
157 advanced analysis, with the same nominal member imperfection amplitude e_0 of $L/1000$ with a half-
158 sinusoidal shape along the member length. The design values adopted in the nominal models for frame
159 and member imperfection amplitudes are reported in Table 1.

160 While the Eurocode design framework requires local imperfections to be incorporated in the
161 developed finite element models [11], the nominal frame models specified in the US and Australian
162 frameworks do not include local imperfections. However, since prEN 1993-1-14 [11] only provides
163 guidance on the magnitudes of local imperfections for outstand elements and distortional buckling in
164 cold-formed sections, the local imperfection amplitudes w_0 given by the modified Dawson & Walker
165 model [25] have been adopted in this paper, as shown in Table 1 for the different cross-sections
166 considered. It should be noted that even for those cases in which local imperfections do not need to be
167 explicitly incorporated in the nominal models (i.e. US and Australian frameworks), the structural
168 analysis models developed in this study for the reliability calibrations incorporate all three
169 imperfections (as described in Section 3) and thus, the influence of the local imperfections is implicitly
170 present in the derived system safety factors (or system resistance factors).

171 *2.1.2. Connection behaviour*

172 Joints of portal frames comprising cold-formed hollow section tubes are complex and often use welded
173 connection solutions, as defined in the CIDECT design guide for RHS connections [26]. The guide
174 includes recommended details for unstiffened and stiffened welded knee connections suitable for rigid
175 portal frames. According to the guide, the rotation capacity of unstiffened connections can be low and
176 thus, stiffened knee connection should be used in structures requiring significant rotational capacity.
177 Test data for stiffened welded knee connections is scarce and limited to carbon steel hollow sections
178 [27-29]. The moment-rotation curves provided in [27] can be reasonably described by a bi-linear curve
179 similar to that shown in Figure 2, which is defined by two stiffness parameters, K_1 and K_2 , and two
180 moment capacities, M_1 and M_2 . Results reported in [27] indicate that while M_1 remained below the
181 plastic capacity of the cross-sections (at approximately 75-80% levels), these stiffened welded
182 connections reached moments exceeding the section flexural capacity by 110-155%. Although there are
183 no equivalent studies of stainless steel stiffened welded connections, recent tests on stainless steel portal
184 frames with RHS sections reported in [30,31] adopted welded column-to-rafter connections with
185 auxiliary steel plates equivalent to those defined in [26,27]. For the connections at the bases in [30,31],
186 steel plates were welded to the bottom edges of the columns, which were then bolted to a pair of load
187 cells. The moment reactions reached during the tests at the bases were below the section capacities, but

188 bending moments comparable to the flexural strength of the sections were attained for some of the
189 specimens at the column-to-rafter (eave) connections.

190 Considering these findings, the connections adopted for the present study represent the behaviour of
191 stiffened welded connections equivalent to those described in [26,27,30,31], and following the approach
192 adopted in [9], the moment-rotation responses of the connections at column bases, eaves and apex have
193 been modelled using the bi-linear curve shown in Figure 2. The parameters defining the nominal
194 connection responses for each frame are summarized in Table 1. The parameters were chosen from the
195 stiffness values reported in [30,31] for similar stainless steel RHS connections and moments M_1 and M_2
196 were adapted from [27] to the flexural capacities of the cross-section geometries and materials adopted
197 in this study. Note that this study does not consider joint failure but assumes the ultimate moment and
198 ductility capacities of the joints are not reached at the failure states of the frames.

199 *2.1.3. Material properties*

200 Stainless steel alloys show pronounced nonlinearity in their stress-strain response with considerable
201 strain-hardening, which is most commonly described through two-stage material models [32,33] and a
202 series of material parameters. Basic nominal material properties for different stainless steel grades such
203 as the Young's modulus E , yield stress f_y , ultimate tensile strength f_u and strain-hardening exponent n
204 are provided in the different structural standards for the Eurocode design framework [2,34], the US
205 framework [20] and the Australian framework [22]. Additional guidance on the modelling of the
206 nonlinear stress-strain response of stainless steel alloys (i.e. to estimate the required additional material
207 parameters such as ultimate strain ϵ_u and the strain-hardening exponent m) is provided in [10,11,20],
208 which was based on the comprehensive studies conducted in [32,33]. Although the yield stress f_y and
209 ultimate tensile strength f_u values provided in structural and material standards correspond to the
210 unformed material, it is well known that cold-formed structural sections undergo significant plastic
211 deformations during manufacturing, which result in a notable increase of the yield stress and a reduction
212 in ductility [36]. Thus, some international design standards already include predictive models to account
213 for these yield stress enhancements [2,34], based on the work presented in [36]. With the aim of
214 developing realistic advanced nominal models, adhering to the provisions given in the different

215 standards, the enhanced material properties of the cold-formed tubes as per [2,34] have been considered
216 in the nominal frame models developed in this study.

217 The values of the nominal material parameters for the stainless steel grades chosen for the present
218 study (austenitic grade EN 1.4301/ASTM 304, duplex grade EN 1.4462/ASTM 2205 and ferritic grade
219 EN 1.4003/ASTM UNS S40977) are summarized in Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 for the Eurocode, US
220 and Australian design frameworks, respectively. Basic material parameters have been directly extracted
221 from the corresponding structural and material Standards, while the remaining parameters, including
222 the enhanced nominal yield stress $f_{y,enh}$, the ultimate strain ϵ_u and the strain-hardening exponent m
223 have been calculated based on the nominal basic material properties and the predictive models given in
224 [10,11,20] and [2,34], respectively. The nominal frame models for the three design frameworks have
225 been built considering enhanced material properties as per the predictive models in [2,34] because
226 considering the basic material parameters for cold-formed elements would result in too conservative
227 predictions of the nominal system strength. Note that since duplex stainless steel grades are currently
228 out of the scope of the AS/NZS 4673 [22] Specification, the basic material properties given in the
229 ASCE 8 [20] Specification for the ASTM 2205 grade have been adopted for Frames 3 and 4 in the
230 Australian design framework (see Table 4). In the same line, the nominal yield stress f_y and ultimate
231 tensile strength f_u values adopted in this study for the ferritic frames (Frames 5 and 6) in the US
232 framework were extracted from the AS/NZS 4673 [22] Specification, since grade EN 1.4003 is not
233 currently covered by ASCE 8 [20].

234 *2.1.4. Residual stresses*

235 Residual stresses in cold-formed stainless steel structural sections are generated during the fabrication
236 processes due to non-uniform plastic deformations, and they can significantly affect the resistance of
237 stainless steel structures [37]. For the cold-formed rectangular hollow section members considered in
238 this paper, membrane residual stresses are low in magnitude and have been shown to have a negligible
239 influence on the structural response, while bending residual stresses are more important [37]. According
240 to prEN 1993-1-14 [11], FE models should include the effect of residual stresses as initial strains or
241 stresses following the appropriate patterns for each section and material type. Similarly, the

242 AS/NZS 4100 [3], AISC 360-16 [4] and AISC 370-21 [10] specifications also state that the numerical
243 models shall include the influence of residual stresses by explicitly modelling these effects in the
244 analysis or by reducing the stiffness of all structural components. prEN 1993-1-14 [11] defines residual
245 stress patterns for a number of cross-section and material types, but since no pattern is given for cold-
246 formed stainless steel SHS and RHS sections, the model proposed in [37] has been adopted in this study.
247 It assumes residual stress magnitudes equal to $0.37f_y$ for the corner regions of the cross-section and
248 $0.63f_y$ for the flat regions, with a rectangular block distribution through thickness and tensile stresses
249 at the outer surfaces of the sections. The same residual stress pattern has also been adopted for the
250 nominal system models developed for the Australian and US design frameworks. In all cases, bending
251 residual stresses were introduced as initial stresses in the finite element models, further details of which
252 are provided in Section 3.1.

253 2.2. FAILURE BEHAVIOUR OF NOMINAL FRAMES

254 The overall dimensions and support conditions of the six stainless steel frames investigated in this paper
255 were chosen to cover different failure modes under gravity loads. It is worth mentioning that although
256 the ultimate failure loads corresponding to the nominal frames for each of the design frameworks
257 investigated were slightly different, as it is further discussed in Section 5.1, the failure modes observed
258 for each frame were essentially identical for the three design frameworks considered.

259 Frames 1, 3 and 5 representing austenitic, duplex and ferritic stainless steel alloys, respectively, have
260 the same overall and cross-section dimensions, with relatively low spans and heights, and compact
261 cross-sections (see Table 1). These frames showed non-sway failure modes associated with spatial
262 yielding at the critical cross-sections, and will allow evaluating the influence of the stainless steel
263 material properties, including strain-hardening, and internal force redistribution in reliability
264 calibrations. The frames showed considerable vertical deflections at the apex sections, while the
265 observed lateral drifts were small. Important influence of material nonlinearity was observed for the
266 frames, especially for the austenitic Frame 1, with a considerable redistribution of internal forces. At
267 the ultimate limit state of the austenitic and ferritic Frames 1 and 5, spatial plastic hinges first formed
268 in the columns near the left and right eave connections, followed by plastic hinges near the apex. The

269 failure of the frames occurred soon thereafter when yielding initiated at the base of the right columns.
270 Despite having the same nominal cross-section, Frame 3 showed remarkably lower redistribution
271 capacity when compared to the equivalent Frames 1 and 5, owing to the considerably higher local
272 slenderness of the cross-section due to the higher yield stress exhibited by duplex stainless steel grades
273 (see Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4). Thus, spatial plastic hinges featuring local buckling deformations
274 were observed sequentially near the right eave, left eave and apex connections for Frame 3, and the
275 frame failed before any yielding was observed at the right column base. In line with the findings
276 reported in [27], local failures were observed on the inside of the eaves connections at advanced stages
277 of frame deformations, and formed in the columns adjacent to the connections. Stresses and local
278 deformations were more pronounced at the right eave for Frames 1, 3 and 5, despite the fact that the
279 loading configuration adopted for these frames was symmetric. Since initial out-of-plumb imperfections
280 were introduced towards the right side of the nominal frames, slightly non-symmetrical failure modes
281 were observed. These imperfections were not sufficient to trigger sway failure modes, given the high
282 rotational stiffness of the bases, but caused slightly higher internal forces at the right columns.

283 On the other hand, Frames 2, 4 and 6 corresponding to austenitic, duplex and ferritic stainless steel
284 alloys exhibit longer spans and pinned support conditions (see Table 1), which resulted in in-plane sway
285 failure modes and allowed evaluating the influence of interaction between material nonlinearities and
286 second order effects in reliability calibrations. The cross-sections comprising these sway frames showed
287 local slenderness values close to the limiting cross-section slenderness between fully effective and
288 slender cross-sections, and thus they were not capable of developing strain-hardening or bending
289 moment redistribution. These frames showed large lateral drifts and vertical deflections at the apex at
290 their respective ultimate limit states, as well as interaction between second order effects and material
291 nonlinearities, particularly for the austenitic Frame 2. Failure occurred when the capacity of the critical
292 cross-sections at the right eave joints was reached, attaining stress levels similar to the corresponding
293 nominal enhanced yield stress $f_{y,enh}$ for each case. At the ultimate limit state, stress values close to
294 $f_{y,enh}$ were also observed in the vicinity of the apex joints. As for the non-sway frames, the global sway

295 imperfections of the nominal frames were introduced towards the right-side of the frames, which
296 triggered the failure of the frames to occur near the right eave connection.

297 **3. FINITE ELEMENT MODELS AND SIMULATIONS**

298 3.1. DEVELOPMENT OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

299 Numerical simulations to estimate the system strengths of stainless steel frames were carried out based
300 on advanced finite element models developed using the general-purpose software ABAQUS [38]. Duo-
301 pitched single-storey, single-bay portal frames equivalent to those described in Section 2, with members
302 comprising cold-formed rectangular hollow sections, were modelled using S4R shell elements. These
303 elements have been widely used in the simulation of cold-formed stainless steel members [39,40] and
304 frames [31].

305 Portal frame models consisted of four independent tubes representing column and rafter members,
306 which were then connected to each other with a system of connector elements available in the ABAQUS
307 library [38] (rigid *BEAM*, *HINGE* and *UJOINT* connector elements), following the approach adopted
308 in [9]. *BEAM* type connectors provide a rigid beam connection between two nodes, while *HINGE* type
309 connectors join the position of two nodes, provide a constraint between one rotational degree of freedom
310 and a rigid behaviour for the remaining degrees of freedom. *UJOINT* type connectors also join the
311 positions of two nodes, but provide a universal constraint between two rotational degrees of freedom.
312 Both *HINGE* and *UJOINT* type connector elements allow assigning different types of user-defined
313 connection behaviours (e.g. elastic, plastic, friction, damage, etc.), but while the *UJOINT* connector
314 element provides a constraint in two rotational degrees of freedom (i.e. rotations about the out-of-plane
315 and in-plane axes), the *HINGE* connector element only constrains one degree of freedom (i.e. rotations
316 about the out-of-plane axis). To model the different connections, five reference points simulating the
317 joint points were first created at the theoretical position of the different joints (base, eave and apex
318 connections), defined as the intersections of the centrelines of adjoining members. Then, each of the
319 end faces of the column and rafter members were kinematically constrained to new reference points
320 located at a distance of 1 mm from the position of the joint reference points, as illustrated in Figure 3.
321 The reference points corresponding to the bottom faces of the columns were connected to the ground
322 reference points through *HINGE* type connector elements constraining rotations about the out-of-plane

323 axes following a user-defined moment-rotation curve, while the reference points from the upper faces
324 of the columns were connected to the eaves joint reference points through rigid *BEAM* type connector
325 elements. The reference points of the bottom faces of the rafters were linked to the eave joint reference
326 points by means of *UJOINT* type connector elements, as shown in Figure 3, which constrained rotations
327 about the out-of-plane axis by user-defined moment-rotation curves while assigning a rigid behaviour
328 to the remaining degrees of freedom. Finally, the apex connections were modelled by a combination of
329 a rigid *BEAM* type connector element (between the reference points corresponding to the upper end
330 face of the left rafter and the apex joint reference points) and a *UJOINT* type connector element
331 (between the apex joint reference points and the reference points corresponding to the upper end face
332 of the right rafter) constraining the out-of-plane axis rotations. Appropriate bi-linear connector
333 behaviour with the corresponding K_1 , K_2 , M_1 and M_2 parameters, as defined in Figure 2, were assigned
334 to each *HINGE* and *UJOINT* connectors (i.e. user-defined moment-rotation curves).

335 The out-of-plane displacement of the points corresponding to the connections of the portal frames
336 with the longitudinal purlins and longitudinal bracings was restrained in the FE models, which
337 corresponded to the apex and eaves joint points, the mid-height sections of the columns and the mid-
338 length sections of the rafters, as indicated in Figure 3. Initial geometric imperfections were introduced
339 following different approaches: while the global out-of-plumb imperfections were defined by directly
340 modifying the position of the relevant finite element nodes, member and local imperfections were
341 introduced from prior linear buckling analyses. In all cases, appropriate imperfection amplitudes were
342 assigned, as indicated in Sections 2.1.1 and 4.1.1 for nominal frames and structural analysis models,
343 respectively.

344 Material properties were assigned through nonlinear true stress vs true plastic strain relationships
345 calculated from the material model given in [10,11,20] with the appropriate material parameters for
346 each case, as discussed in Section 2.1.3. Additionally, residual stresses were introduced in the finite
347 element models as initial stresses using the **INITIAL CONDITIONS, TYPE-STRESS* option in
348 ABAQUS [38], with the stress pattern and magnitude adopted from the model proposed in [37] for
349 cold-formed rectangular hollow sections. Gravity loads were applied at the upper faces of the rafters as
350 *TRVEC* surface traction loads with the appropriate downwards direction and finally, the geometrically

351 and materially nonlinear analyses were performed using the Static Riks method until the collapse of the
352 frames was reached. Due to the extensive computational effort required for the finite element
353 simulations, to minimise the computing time while ensuring accurate solutions, a mesh convergence
354 study was performed prior to running the simulations for two of the frames investigated, Frames 1 and
355 2. The mesh convergence study indicated that a mesh size of approximately 25 mm × 25 mm, with
356 around 20,000 elements, provided the most suitable compromise between computational cost and
357 accuracy of the results.

358 3.2. VALIDATION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

359 The developed finite element model was validated against the tests conducted by Arrayago et al. [30,31]
360 on austenitic single-span, single-storey stainless steel frames with flat roofs and cold-formed
361 rectangular hollow sections. Although this Section only describes the key aspects of the experimental
362 programme, more detailed information can be found in [30,31]. The frames tested were 2 m high and
363 spanned 4 m, and were subjected to vertical and horizontal loading conditions: frames were first loaded
364 with two vertical point loads at the rafters, and an imposed displacement was subsequently applied at
365 the support bases while maintaining the vertical loads constant at the second loading step. Thus, the
366 developed ABAQUS script was slightly modified to replicate the geometry and loading conditions
367 adopted in the tests, although the main considerations discussed in the previous Section were still valid.
368 The material properties defined in the finite element model were those obtained from tensile coupon
369 tests and reported in [30,31]. The influence of residual stresses was implicitly included in the validation
370 models through the material properties adopted, since the stress vs strain curves were obtained from
371 tensile tests. According to [41,42], coupons curve longitudinally when cut from cold-formed tubes as
372 bending residual stresses are released, but return to their original straight shape when gripped and loaded
373 in a tensile testing machine. Thus, it can be assumed that during this straightening process the bending
374 residual stresses are re-introduced into the coupons and consequently, they do not need to be explicitly
375 incorporated into the FE models. Likewise, global sway imperfections with the measured amplitudes
376 were introduced in the models, combined with the reference amplitudes of L/1000 for initial member
377 imperfections [11], since no information was available on the amplitude of these imperfections.

378 The welded rafter-to-column connections in the experimental specimens were stiffened using
379 welded steel plates, and hence were modelled as rigid knee connections by assigning high initial
380 stiffness values K_1 to the bi-linear models described in Section 2.1.2. Similarly, the rotational stiffness
381 values measured from experimental results and reported in [30,31] were assigned to the base
382 connections. Following the experimental set-up, the out-of-plane displacement of the loading sections
383 and the right knee connections was restrained, as was the horizontal in-plane displacement of the
384 reference point at the right rafter-to-column connection joint. Vertical loads were applied as point loads
385 at the indicated locations [30,31] and the horizontal loading was introduced by imposing a prescribed
386 displacement at the column supports. Finite element analyses were performed in two steps, following
387 the experimental approach: for the first step the Static General method was employed to solve the
388 geometrically and materially nonlinear analyses, while for the second horizontal loading step the Static
389 Riks method was adopted.

390 The comparison between the experimental and numerical vertical load-deflection and horizontal
391 load-displacement curves is presented in Figure 4 for the four specimens reported in [30,31], while
392 Table 5 reports the numerical-to-experimental load ratios for the vertical and horizontal loading steps
393 ($F_{v,FE}/F_{v,exp}$ and $F_{h,FE}/F_{h,exp}$), as well as for the vertical deflection and horizontal displacement ratios
394 ($d_{v,FE}/d_{v,exp}$ and $d_{h,FE}/d_{h,exp}$). The calculated mean ratios and corresponding coefficients of variation
395 (COV), in conjunction with the load-displacement histories reported in Figure 4, indicate that the
396 developed FE model is capable of accurately replicating the behaviour of the stainless steel frames.

397 **4. SYSTEM STRENGTH RELIABILITY CALIBRATIONS**

398 This Section presents the adopted statistical models for the random variables that mainly affect the
399 system strength of stainless steel structures as well as the loads. The Section also provides a description
400 of the methodology used in the reliability calibration of portal frames under gravity loads for the
401 Eurocode and US/Australian design frameworks.

402 **4.1. STATISTICS OF UNCERTAIN VARIABLES**

403 *4.1.1. Variables affecting the resistance*

404 In the calibration of the system partial safety factors and system resistance factors for stainless steel
405 frames, the system strength distributions were estimated from extensive simulations that accounted for

406 the variability of the different geometric and material random variables defining the frames. The
407 statistics of the random variables, including geometric properties, imperfections, residual stresses and
408 connection stiffness are summarized in Table 6, while the variability models for the material parameters
409 are reported in Table 7 for the three stainless steel families investigated.

410 The statistical characteristics of the random variables defining the cross-section geometry (H , B and
411 t), member (e_0) and local (γ_2) imperfections, and the amplification factor Y for residual stress
412 distributions in stainless steel RHS specimens adopted in this study were extracted from [43], in which
413 extensive databases on stainless steel structural members were collated and analysed, and suitable
414 probabilistic models were proposed. Note that the residual stress pattern has been assumed to be
415 deterministic in this study, but assigned a random magnitude by applying a random amplification factor
416 Y to the stress distribution values defined in the model proposed in [37]. Although measurements on
417 stainless steel frame imperfections exist [30,31], they are very limited and insufficient to estimate the
418 stochastic variability of the out-of-plumbness ϕ . However, since the fabrication workshops for stainless
419 steel structures are generally specialized and high-end, it can be assumed that the distributions provided
420 for frame imperfection amplitudes in cold-formed carbon steel frames represent an upper bound for
421 stainless steel structural frames. From a significantly broader database of measurements, a normal out-
422 of-plumb angle distribution is proposed in [9] with a mean and a standard deviation of zero and $1/610$,
423 respectively, to characterize frame imperfection uncertainties in carbon steel frames (see Table 6).
424 Similarly, without available measurements to characterize the variability of the parameters defining the
425 behaviour of stainless steel stiffened welded connections, the models accounting for the uncertainties
426 related to the K_1 , K_2 , M_1 and M_2 parameters (as discussed in Section 2.1.2) were chosen based on the
427 information available in the literature for steel connections. Following the assumptions made in [9] to
428 characterize the variability of cold-formed joints, this study also assumes that the means of the K_1 , K_2 ,
429 M_1 and M_2 parameters are equal to their nominal values and that they can be modelled by log-normal
430 distributions, as reported in Table 6. The coefficients of variation adopted in the present study have also
431 been based on the values assumed in [9], with a COV of 0.30 for the initial stiffness K_1 , which shows
432 the largest uncertainty relative to the other parameters defining the behaviour of connections, and COVs
433 of 0.15, 0.10 and 0.15 for K_2 , M_1 and M_2 , respectively.

434 The statistical characterization of the material parameters defining the stress-strain behaviour of
435 stainless steel alloys is summarized in Table 7, based on the results reported in [43]. Note that the
436 overstrength ratios (mean-to-nominal ratios) for the enhanced yield stress $f_{y,enh}$ and ultimate tensile
437 strength f_u reported in Table 7 refer to the nominal values corresponding to the European structural and
438 material standards [2,34,35], which implies that the equivalent overstrength ratios relative to the ASCE 8
439 [20] or AS/NZS 4673 [22] specifications would be higher owing to the lower nominal values codified in
440 these standards (as per the values reported in Table 2 against those given in Table 3 and Table 4). Although
441 this study uses the European yield stress f_y and ultimate tensile strength f_u as reference values to model
442 the actual f_y and f_u values, it would have been possible to follow alternative approaches based on the
443 ASCE 8 [20] or AS/NZS 4673 [22] nominal values and associated overstrength ratios.

444 The analysis presented in this paper assumed deterministic overall frame properties (frame span,
445 column height and height at apex), while perfect correlation between all members for the random cross-
446 sectional properties (height H , width B and thickness t), material properties (Young's modulus E , yield
447 stress f_y , ultimate tensile strength f_u , ultimate strain ϵ_u and strain-hardening exponents n and m) and
448 residual stress magnitudes were adopted. The assumption of perfect correlation has been shown to be
449 usually conservative for reliability evaluations [6]. Additionally, member and local imperfections and
450 the parameters governing the behaviour of connections (K_1 , K_2 , M_1 and M_2) were defined as random
451 variables with no correlation.

452 *4.1.2. Model uncertainty*

453 One of the most important stochastic variables in the calibration of safety or resistance factors for direct
454 analysis is model uncertainty. Model uncertainty arises from assumptions and approximations made in
455 determining the strength of a structure using advanced FE models and might have a substantial influence
456 on the computed resistances [44]. Thus, it is important that it is considered in reliability analyses.
457 According to prEN 1993-1-14, Annex A [11], the model uncertainty for advanced analysis γ_{FE} or θ can
458 be estimated by comparing experimental data to the results predicted from advanced analysis, provided
459 that the experimental specimen is similar in the failure mode and in the controlling parameters (relative
460 slenderness, post-buckling behaviour, geometric nonlinearity, material characterisation, etc.). In those

461 cases in which experimental results are available, the model factor may be calculated based on statistical
462 evaluations according to the rules given in the EN 1990 Annex D [45], as per clause (4) in prEN 1993-
463 1-14, Annex A [11]. However, for the case of complex structural systems such as frames, the availability
464 of experimental results to be adopted as benchmarks are considerably scarce, and in such cases more
465 generic statistical characterizations found in the literature need to be adopted for model uncertainties.
466 The approaches adopted by different authors to account for model uncertainty include unbiased normal
467 distributions with a COV of 0.05 [8] and log-normal distributions with a mean and COV of 1.0 and
468 0.05, respectively [46,47].

469 The finite element model developed for the present study was validated against four tests on stainless
470 steel frames, as described in Section 3.2, with a mean and COV of the FE-to-experimental results equal
471 to 1.02 and 0.024, respectively (see Table 5). Although these results indicate that the FE models were
472 capable of replicating the behaviour of stainless steel frame tests, there was insufficient information to
473 derive a probabilistic characterization of the model uncertainty. Thus, the model uncertainty statistics
474 adopted in this study for the reliability calibrations were assumed to be log-normally distributed with
475 mean and COV of 1.0 and 0.05 [46,47]. In order to incorporate the model uncertainty in the statistics
476 of the frame strength, simulation results were combined with the model uncertainty by multiplying each
477 simulated system strength by a randomly generated value of model uncertainty factor [8] based on a
478 log-normal distribution with mean of 1.0 and a COV of 0.05.

479 *4.1.3. Load statistics*

480 The statistical distributions adopted in the literature for gravity loads (i.e. permanent (dead) loads and
481 imposed (live) loads) in the different design frameworks tend to be consistent in terms of the distribution
482 types adopted, although have considerably different mean-to-nominal and COV values, especially for
483 imposed loads. This can be explained by the limited amount of available imposed load surveys and the
484 considerably different nominal imposed load values prescribed for equivalent floor uses in international
485 standards EN 1991-1-1 [48], ASCE 7 [49] and AS/NZS 1170.1 [50]. In general, the permanent loads
486 are assumed to be normally distributed with mean values equal or very close to the characteristic or
487 nominal value of the action and small coefficients of variation for the three design frameworks
488 considered [46,47,51], as per the values reported in Table 8. Imposed live loads are the most uncertain

489 of the stochastic variables, and although different studies and authors consistently adopt Extreme Type
490 I (Gumbel) statistical distributions, a variety of mean-to-nominal and COV values can be found in the
491 literature. For the US framework, most studies have adopted a mean-to-nominal value equal to 1.0 with
492 a COV of 0.25 for imposed loads [5,6,8,51], while for the Eurocode framework the literature includes
493 mean-to-nominal values ranging between 0.40, 0.60 and 0.70, with coefficients of variations between
494 0.2 and 0.6 [46,52,53].

495 The approach followed in this study to define the mean-to-nominal and COV values for imposed
496 loads in the different design frameworks was to use the nominal values provided in each relevant load
497 standard (i.e. EN 1991-1-1 [48], ASCE 7 [49] and AS/NZS 1170.1 [50] for the Eurocode, US and
498 Australian frameworks, respectively). Following the recommendations in [48,49,50], the nominal load
499 values were multiplied by reduction factors that account for different tributary areas, which are also
500 slightly different in the three loading standards. For each category of floor use defined in EN 1991-1-1
501 [48] (including residential activities, office areas, restaurants, theatres, museums, gymnastic rooms and
502 shopping areas) the reduced nominal imposed loads were calculated for the three load standards and for
503 tributary areas ranging between 50-200 m², and averaged reduced nominal loads were calculated for
504 this range of areas for each standard to produce imposed loads $q_{k,i,av}(EN)$, $q_{n,i,av}(ASCE)$ and
505 $q_{n,i,av}(AS/NZS)$, where i represents the different floor use categories. Loads for the US framework were
506 normalized for each category by the corresponding reduced nominal loads according to the Eurocode
507 and Australian frameworks, $q_{n,i,av}(ASCE)/q_{k,i,av}(EN)$ and $q_{n,i,av}(ASCE)/q_{k,i,av}(AS/NZS)$, and finally
508 averaged load ratios were calculated from the different floor use categories.

509 Results indicated that, on average, imposed live loads corresponding to the US framework represent
510 80% of the loads in the Eurocode framework, while similar values were obtained for the US and the
511 Australian design frameworks. From these relationships, the mean-to-nominal values adopted for the
512 reliability calibrations derived in this study corresponded to 1.0 for the US and the Australian design
513 frameworks and 0.80 for the Eurocode framework; i.e. EN 1991-1-1 [48], the standard with the most
514 conservative (highest) nominal loads on average. For the three cases, the same coefficient of variation
515 of 0.25 and an Extreme Type I distribution were adopted [51]. The adoption of a mean-to-nominal

516 imposed load equal to 0.80 for the Eurocode framework is more conservative than some of the values
517 reported in the literature, which results in lower values of estimated probabilities of failure [46,52,53].
518 The information about the final statistical distributions adopted for imposed live loads in the three
519 design frameworks is summarized in Table 8.

520 4.2. SYSTEM RELIABILITY ANALYSIS METHOD

521 The most commonly accepted approach to quantify the safety of a structure is to determine its
522 probability of failure P_f (i.e. the probability of loads Q exceeding the structural resistance R or reaching
523 a certain limit state). This probability of failure or structural reliability can be evaluated through direct
524 Monte Carlo simulations [55], but since such simulations generally require prohibitive computational
525 effort, the study presented in this paper is based on the more efficient reliability analysis method
526 proposed in [6], which is summarized in this section.

527 The probability of failure of a structural system can be determined from $P_f = P(R - Q \leq 0)$, where
528 R is the system resistance and Q represents the loads applied. By defining the limit state function $g =$
529 $R - Q$, then $P_f = P(g \leq 0)$, since $g \leq 0$ defines the failure domain. Seeing that this paper intends to
530 extend the Direct Design Method to stainless steel frames for three different design frameworks (the
531 Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks), the three different load combinations given in Eq. 3 to Eq.
532 5 have been considered, as prescribed in EN 1990 [45], ASCE 7 [49] and AS/NZS 1170.0 [54],
533 respectively. In these equations G_k , D_n and G_n represent permanent (dead) loads while Q_k , L_n and Q_n
534 refer to imposed (live) loads. Note that the subscripts “k” and “n” emphasize that these loads are the
535 characteristic or nominal values provided in the relevant codes, and that load notations consistent with
536 the different standards have been adopted for the corresponding design frameworks.

$$\text{Eurocode framework:} \quad 1.35G_k + 1.50Q_k \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\text{US framework:} \quad 1.20D_n + 1.60L_n \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\text{Australian framework:} \quad 1.20G_n + 1.50Q_n \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

537 The limit state functions are reformulated to account for permanent loads and imposed loads as per $g =$
538 $R - G - Q$ or $g^* = R - D - L$, and the probability of failure of each structural system can be computed
539 following the steps listed below. Note that only a summary of the procedure is provided in this paper,
540

541 since the adopted methodology has been extensively reported in the literature [5,6,8,9]. However, the
 542 DDM methodology has only been applied to the Australian and US design frameworks, and thus the
 543 details for its extension to the Eurocode framework are highlighted:

- 544 (1) Determine the probabilistic models (distribution type and parameters) for the system resistance R
 545 under gravity loads accounting for all the relevant uncertainties. For this, extensive simulations are
 546 carried out using the finite element model described in Section 3 and the statistics of the random
 547 variables reported in Section 4.1. By adopting the Latin-Hypercube sampling (LHS) technique, the
 548 number of required simulations to determine the probabilistic models for R is reduced to 200 cases
 549 per frame.
- 550 (2) Re-write the LRFD design equations (Eq. 1 and Eq. 2) for the gravity load combinations
 551 considered in the Eurocode, US and Australian design frameworks as per Eq. 6 to Eq. 8, in which
 552 $\gamma_{M,s}$ is the system safety factor and ϕ_s is the system resistance factor.

Eurocode framework:
$$\frac{R_k}{\gamma_{M,s}} = 1.35G_k + 1.50Q_k \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

US framework:
$$\phi_s R_n = 1.20D_n + 1.60L_n \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

Australian framework:
$$\phi_s R_n = 1.20G_n + 1.50Q_n \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

- 553
 554 (3) For a range of $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s values, define the relationship between the nominal resistance R_n and
 555 the nominal permanent and imposed gravity loads through the Load Scale Method and the LRFD
 556 design equations [12]. The nominal loads G_k , Q_k , D_n , L_n , G_n and Q_n can be re-written in terms of
 557 the characteristic or nominal resistances R_k and R_n as per in Eq. 9 to Eq. 11, where α is the
 558 imposed-to-permanent (live-to-dead) load ratio, $\alpha = Q_k/G_k$, $\alpha = L_n/D_n$ or $\alpha = Q_n/G_n$.

Eurocode framework:
$$G_k = \frac{R_k}{\gamma_{M,s}(1.35+1.50\alpha)} \quad \text{and} \quad Q_k = \frac{\alpha R_k}{\gamma_{M,s}(1.35+1.50\alpha)} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

US framework:
$$D_n = \frac{\phi_s R_n}{1.20+1.60\alpha} \quad \text{and} \quad L_n = \frac{\alpha \phi_s R_n}{1.20+1.60\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

Australian framework:
$$G_n = \frac{\phi_s R_n}{1.20+1.50\alpha} \quad \text{and} \quad Q_n = \frac{\alpha \phi_s R_n}{1.20+1.50\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

- 559
 560 (4) Re-define the probabilistic models for permanent and imposed loads from the relationships defined
 561 in Step (3) and the models available in the literature and reported in Table 8.

562 (5) Compute the probability of failure P_f using the First-Order Reliability Method (FORM) [55]. The
563 reliability index β is commonly adopted as a measurement of the probability of failure, and can be
564 calculated for each value of $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s considered. The reliability index is related to the
565 probability of failure P_f through $\beta = \Phi^{-1}(1 - P_f)$, where Φ^{-1} is the inverse standard normal
566 distribution function.

567 Using the reliability analysis method described above, system reliability indices β can be computed and
568 the relationships between system reliability indices β and system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ or system resistance
569 factors ϕ_s can be established for a range of imposed-to-permanent (live-to-dead) load ratios α . This is
570 addressed in the following section for the six stainless steel frames investigated in this paper.

571 **5. RELIABILITY CALIBRATION RESULTS FOR THE ULTIMATE LIMIT STATE**

572 This Section presents the results for the reliability calibration of stainless steel frames subjected to
573 gravity loads. The system strength distributions are provided first for the six portal frames, and the
574 reliability calibration results corresponding to the Eurocode, US and Australian frameworks are
575 subsequently presented and compared.

576 **5.1. SYSTEM STRENGTH OF STAINLESS STEEL FRAMES UNDER GRAVITY LOADS**

577 System strength distributions for stainless steel frames under gravity loads were obtained from
578 numerical simulations accounting for the variability of the random variables defined in Section 4.1 and
579 using the FE models described in Section 3. The ultimate loads of the frames were determined from the
580 load-vertical deflection curves obtained from the finite element simulations for the apex joint reference
581 points: for those frames showing load-deflection curves with a clear peak point, this peak load was
582 adopted as the ultimate load; on the contrary, where no clear peak point existed the load at which the
583 stiffness of the curve fell below a value of 5% of the initial stiffness was defined as the ultimate load
584 [9,56]. It is worth noting that the ultimate loads of frames showing sway failure modes (Frames 2, 4
585 and 6) were typically obtained as the peak loads, while for those frames reaching advanced stages of
586 yielding (Frames 1, 3 and 5) the stiffness limit criteria governed. The histograms for the system
587 strengths are reported in Figure 5 for the six frames analysed, and suggest the system strengths of frames
588 under gravity loads can be accurately fitted by log-normal distributions, consistent with those obtained

589 in other studies [6,8,9,13]. The fit of the log-normal distributions was carried out by means of the
590 Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox in MATLAB [57], based on the maximum likelihood method.
591 The Anderson-Darling (AD) goodness-of-fit tests were used to evaluate the resulting distributions at
592 the 5% significance level [58]. It is important to highlight that the obtained system strength distributions
593 are valid for the analysis of the structural reliability of stainless steel frames regardless of the design
594 framework considered, since they are based on the geometric, material, imperfection and connection
595 properties defined from probabilistic models established from measurements on real stainless steel
596 structures and members. The differences between the reliability calibration results presented in the next
597 sections result from the different nominal system resistances obtained for each design framework, as
598 well as from the different load combinations and load statistics assumed for the three frameworks.

599 Mean values of the system strengths R_m and corresponding COVs are summarized in Table 9,
600 together with the nominal frame resistances for the three design frameworks investigated in this study
601 $R_{k,EN}$, $R_{n,US}$ and $R_{n,AU}$, which were determined from finite element simulations following Sections 2.1
602 and 3, and the corresponding mean-to-nominal resistance ratios $R_m/R_{n,i}$. The results in Table 9 show
603 that the nominal resistances are very similar regardless the adopted design framework for Frames 5 and
604 6, since the nominal material properties are similar for ferritic stainless steels in the Eurocode and
605 Australian/US frameworks. However, for the remaining frames representing austenitic (Frames 1 and
606 2) and duplex (Frames 3 and 4) stainless steels, the nominal resistances are lower for the Australian/US
607 frameworks than for the Eurocode framework owing to the significantly lower nominal material
608 properties specified for the considered EN 1.4301/ASTM 304 and EN 1.4462/ASTM 2205 grades, as
609 per the yield stress values reported in Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. Analysing the mean-to-nominal
610 resistance ratios reported in Table 9, it is evident that austenitic and ferritic stainless steel frames failing
611 in non-sway modes (Frames 1 and 5) present a higher strength reserve (i.e. higher mean-to-nominal
612 resistance ratios) than the frames failing in sway modes (Frames 2 and 6) due to the partial load
613 redistribution occurring in the non-sway frames and the overstrength ratios that these stainless steel
614 families present (see Table 7). On the contrary, the $R_m/R_{n,i}$ strength reserve in the case of the non-sway
615 duplex Frame 3 is lower than for the other stainless steel non-sway frames (Frames 1 and 5) due to the
616 limited redistribution capacity of this frame, as discussed in Section 2.2, and the lower overstrength

617 ratios exhibited by duplex stainless steels. Consequently, the $R_m/R_{n,i}$ ratios observed for the duplex
618 stainless steel Frame 3 and Frame 4 are equal within each design framework. The results also indicate
619 that the uncertainty (COV) of the system resistance of all frames is around 0.09-0.12. Note that the
620 higher mean-to-nominal resistance ratios observed for Frames 1 to 4 in the US and Australian
621 frameworks are caused by the lower nominal material properties provided for austenitic and duplex
622 grades in the ASCE 8 [20] and AS/NZS 4673 [22] specifications.

623 5.2. RELIABILITY CALIBRATION RESULTS FOR FRAMES UNDER GRAVITY LOADS

624 Following the procedure described in Section 4.2, the results of the reliability calibrations for stainless
625 steel portal frames under gravity loads are presented in this Section for the three design frameworks.
626 These results are based on the probabilistic models for system resistance presented in Section 5.1 and
627 the nominal system resistances calculated according to the relevant provisions for each design
628 framework, as discussed in Section 2.

629 Derived $\beta - \gamma_{M,s}$ curves for the Eurocode design framework are presented in Figure 6 for the six
630 stainless steel portal frames investigated in this paper, considering different imposed-to-permanent load
631 ratios Q_k/G_k . While the imposed-to-permanent load ratio typically ranges from 0.5 to 4.0 [59], the
632 common load ratio for hollow section steel structures is $Q_k/G_k = 2.0$ [8]. Consequently, this study
633 assumed imposed-to-permanent load ratios close to 2.0, between 1.0 and 3.0. In the figure, the target
634 reliability index $\beta_0 = 3.8$ corresponding to the minimum value recommended in EN 1990 [45] for CC2
635 consequence class structures for a 50-year reference period for the ultimate limit state is also indicated,
636 which is commonly considered in reliability analyses carried out in the Eurocode framework. The
637 results shown in Figure 6 demonstrate that the reliability index β increases with increasing system safety
638 factor $\gamma_{M,s}$, as would be expected, while for a given value of system safety factor $\gamma_{M,s}$ the reliability
639 index β decreases as the imposed-to-permanent load ratio Q_k/G_k increases. This is because imposed
640 loads show higher variability than permanent loads (see statistical parameters in Table 8) and thus not
641 only is the reliability of a structure dependent on the imposed-to-permanent load ratio, but the reliability
642 reduces when the variable loads become dominant.

643 Likewise, Figure 7 and Figure 8 present the $\beta - \phi_s$ curves derived for the six stainless steel portal
644 frames for the US and Australian design frameworks, respectively, for the same imposed-to-permanent
645 load ratios L_n/D_n or Q_n/G_n as those considered for the Eurocode framework. The target reliability
646 index $\beta_0 = 2.5$ is included in the figures for the US and Australian design frameworks since this target
647 reliability index has been historically adopted for steel structures in the US and Australian frameworks
648 [60,61]. The curves shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8 decrease with increasing system resistance factor
649 ϕ_s , which is the opposite trend to that observed in Figure 6 for the Eurocode design framework, because
650 the resistance factor is equivalent to the inverse of the safety factor $\gamma_{M,S}$. However, it can be seen that
651 for a given value of resistance factor ϕ_s the reliability index decreases with increasing values of L_n/D_n
652 or Q_n/G_n , as also found for the Eurocode framework. Comparisons between the $\beta - \gamma_{M,S}$ and the
653 $\beta - \phi_s$ curves derived for the different design frameworks indicate that the values of the derived
654 reliability indices are generally lower in Figure 7 and Figure 8 than for the Eurocode design framework
655 in Figure 6 for equivalent design situations, suggesting that the Eurocode design framework may be a
656 more conservative design approach than the US and Australian frameworks. This finding is further
657 investigated in the following Section.

658 5.3. COMPARISON, DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

659 This Section presents a comparison between the reliability calibrations corresponding to the three
660 design frameworks investigated in this paper and a discussion of the reliability index β values obtained
661 for the different frames. Subsequently, recommendations for the system safety factor $\gamma_{M,S}$ and resistance
662 factors ϕ_s to be adopted for the analysis-based design of stainless steel frames under gravity loads are
663 provided.

664 Figure 9 compares the derived $\beta - \gamma_{M,S}$ curves corresponding to the Eurocode framework for the six
665 stainless steel frames analysed in this paper with the equivalent $\beta - 1/\phi_s$ curves for the US and
666 Australian frameworks. In the figure, each frame is represented by a different colour, while each design
667 framework is plotted with a different line style. Since the reliability index β depends on the imposed-
668 to-permanent load ratio Q_k/G_k , it is not possible to achieve a uniform level of reliability for different
669 Q_k/G_k ratios with a single value of $\gamma_{M,S}$ or ϕ_s . Equally, it would not be practical for engineering practice

670 to have different safety factors for different load ratios. Thus, the results presented in Figure 9 are for
671 the imposed-to-permanent load ratio of $Q_k/G_k = 2$ (or $L_n/D_n = 2$, $Q_n/G_n = 2$), which corresponds
672 to a typical load ratio for hollow section steel structures [8]. Four different target reliability indices β_0
673 have been highlighted in the Figure: 3.8, 3.3, 3.0 and 2.5. The first two values (3.8 and 3.3) correspond
674 to the minimum values recommended in EN 1990 [45] for consequence classes CC2 and CC1, while
675 values 3.0 and 2.5 refer to the target reliability indices traditionally adopted in the US and Australian
676 frameworks [60,61]. The probabilities of failure corresponding to these target reliability indices are
677 $7.23 \cdot 10^{-05}$, $4.83 \cdot 10^{-04}$, $1.35 \cdot 10^{-03}$ and $6.21 \cdot 10^{-03}$, respectively.

678 From the $\beta - \gamma_{M,S}$ and $\beta - 1/\phi_s$ curves reported in Figure 9 it can be appreciated that the Eurocode
679 framework is the one providing the highest reliability indices owing to the lower 0.80 mean-to-nominal
680 values adopted by this framework for the imposed variable load (see Table 8), which means that the
681 nominal imposed loads specified in EN 1991-1-1 [48] are in general more conservative than for the
682 equivalent load standards ASCE 7 [49] and AS/NZS 1170.1 [50]. The relatively high reliability indices
683 for the Eurocode are followed by the US framework, and the lowest indices are observed for the
684 Australian framework. Given that the US and Australian frameworks adopt the same mean-to-nominal
685 values for the imposed loads (as shown in Table 8), differences between the US and Australian
686 $\beta - 1/\phi_s$ curves can be explained by the slightly more conservative load combination adopted by the
687 ASCE 7 [49] Specification over the AS/NZS 1170.0 [54] standard, as indicated by the load factors
688 affecting the imposed loads in Eq. 4 and Eq. 5. Despite the differences observed between the three
689 design frameworks, the relative reliability indices obtained for the six stainless steel frames are similar
690 within each of the design frameworks, and are consistent with the mean-to-nominal resistance ratios
691 $R_m/R_{n,i}$ reported in Table 9. The lowest reliability levels are observed in all frameworks for the frames
692 showing sway failure modes (Frames 2, 4 and 6), while the $\beta - \gamma_{M,S}$ curves for frames showing non-
693 sway failure modes (Frames 1, 3 and 5) are typically higher. However, the high overstrength ratios
694 (mean-to-nominal yield stress ratios) for austenitic and duplex alloys result in higher reliability indices
695 for Frames 1, 2, 4 and 5 in the US and Australian frameworks. The adoption of more accurate and

696 consistent nominal yield stress values across the different design frameworks would lead to more
697 uniform reliabilities for the different stainless steel families.

698 There is a wide variation of target reliability indices adopted by the different standards, which can
699 be attributed to historical reasons. When building design codes switched from allowable stress design
700 to the LRFD format in the late 1980's, different research works were carried out to determine the level
701 of safety embodied in the existing building codes for different construction materials, components
702 (beams, columns, joints), loads and types of buildings [62]. Based on the reliability indices derived,
703 safety factors were calibrated for the load and resistance factored design (LRFD), aiming to obtain
704 reliability levels that differed as little as possible from the historically evolved and accepted levels
705 (which would result in a minimum change in design practice) and to provide as small a scatter as
706 possible with regard to the target value of β_0 . The variability observed between the various studies was
707 large, and so was the scatter between various materials, types of components and types of loads. For
708 example, the values of β ranged between 2.2 and 6.1, with an average value of 3.8, in the study
709 conducted by Vrouwenvelder and Siemes [63] for buildings in the Netherlands, while an average value
710 of 3.0 was obtained by Galambos et al. [64] for the US. The first drafts of the Eurocodes adopted the
711 commonly accepted value of $\beta_0 = 3.8$ for 50 years as an appropriate target value for CC2 consequence
712 class structures [62], while the significantly lower value of $\beta_0 = 3.0$ was chosen in the ASCE 7 [49]
713 Specification for Risk Category II structures to provide not only protection against structural failure,
714 but also against property and economic damage for small events; however, the Commentary of the
715 Standard states that at the present time there is no documentation justifying the reliability intended. The
716 probability of failure associated with $\beta_0 = 3.8$ is about 20 times lower than that for $\beta_0 = 3.0$. However,
717 it should be noticed that these target reliability indices are intended for the design of new structures,
718 and not for the assessment of existing structures; strengthening existing structures is more costly and
719 such structures will typically have service lives shorter than 50 years, and thus lower reliability targets
720 can be accepted [62].

721 Table 10 summarizes the required system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s
722 derived for the different design frameworks and the four target reliability indices considered in the

723 analysis, $\beta_0 = 3.8, 3.3, 3.0$ and 2.5 , corresponding to the imposed-to-permanent load ratio of $Q_k/G_k =$
724 2 . For comparison purposes, the inverse values of the reported system safety factors $1/\gamma_{M,s}$ and system
725 resistance factors $1/\phi_s$ are also included as comparable measures of equivalent system resistance
726 factors ϕ_s and system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$, respectively. It is worth noting that some of the system safety
727 factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ reported in Table 10 for the Eurocode framework show values below unity, particularly for
728 the lowest target reliability indices considered. This means that the resistance reserve $R_m/R_{k,EN}$ existing
729 in the investigated stainless steel frames is sufficient to meet some of the lowest reliability requirements
730 without the need to apply additional resistance reduction through the $\gamma_{M,s}$ factor, which can be attributed
731 to the high yield overstrength ratios generally obtained for stainless steels (see values reported in Table
732 7), or equivalently, to the excessively low nominal yield stress values considered in the standards.
733 Likewise, and for similar reasons, some of the system resistance factors ϕ_s shown in Table 10 are above
734 unity for the lowest target reliability indices analysed for the US and Australian frameworks. Note that
735 the results reported in Table 10 were calculated accounting for model uncertainties as described in
736 Section 4.1.2. Equivalent analyses without considering model uncertainty produced uncertainty (COV)
737 of the system resistance of all frames in the range from 0.07 to 0.10 ; lower than the range (0.09 – 0.12)
738 obtained in Section 5.1 when model uncertainty was considered. The lower uncertainty of the system
739 resistance resulted in an average 2.5% change of the system safety factors and system resistance factors
740 reported in Table 10.

741 The required system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ reported in Table 10 for the target reliability index of $\beta_0 =$
742 3.8 prescribed in EN 1990 [45] range between 1.10 and 1.17 , with the lowest values aligned with non-
743 sway frames (Frames 1, 3 and 5). Similarly, to meet a target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 2.5 - 3.0$ for the
744 US and Australian frameworks, system resistance factors ϕ_s ranging between 0.88 – 1.02 and 0.85 – 0.97
745 would be required, respectively. On average, to achieve a $\beta_0 = 3.8$ value for stainless steel frames under
746 gravity loads a $\gamma_{M,s}$ of 1.15 may be adopted for the Eurocode framework, while ϕ_s factors of 0.95 and
747 0.90 are recommended for the US and Australian frameworks, respectively. Note that the inverse of the
748 system safety factor proposed for the Eurocode framework $1/1.15=0.87$ is not far from the resistance
749 factors 0.90 and 0.95 recommended for the US and Australian frameworks. It should be also noted that

750 the recommended $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s factors are to be used only when designing stainless steel frames under
751 gravity loads. Since calibrations for other load combinations including wind loads typically show lower
752 reliability indices than for structures in which gravity loads govern [65], independent calibrations are
753 necessary for stainless steel frames under combined gravity and wind loads for the recommendation of
754 suitable $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s factors.

755 6. CONCLUSIONS

756 System-based design approaches represent a change in the paradigm of structural design with a strong
757 potential not only for the design of lighter and more efficient new structures, but also for the
758 reassessment and reinforcement of existing structures. Provisions for *analysis-by-design* approaches
759 have been incorporated in several international design codes for steel structures [3,4,10], but no specific
760 reliability requirements or acceptable target reliability indices are provided for structural systems.
761 Although system-based design recommendations have been proposed for different types of steel
762 structures, including hot-rolled and cold-formed frames, as well as rack and scaffolding structures, in
763 the form of the Direct Design Method (DDM), the Method has not yet been extended to stainless steel
764 structures, and there is no developed system reliability framework for this material. This paper presents
765 the first step in the extension of the DDM to stainless steel structures, presenting system reliability
766 analyses for stainless steel portal frames under gravity loads using advanced nonlinear numerical
767 simulations.

768 The system reliability calibration is based on six typical single-bay, single-storey stainless steel
769 portal frames, which cover different failure modes and the three most common stainless steel grades
770 (austenitic EN 1.4301/ASTM 304, duplex EN 1.4462/ASTM 2205 and ferritic EN 1.4003/ASTM UNS
771 S40977 grades). The study was based on extensive finite element simulations that accounted for the
772 variability of the random variables affecting the system resistance (including geometric properties,
773 imperfections, material properties, connection behaviour and model uncertainty), from which the
774 probabilistic characteristics of the ultimate frame strengths under gravity loads were determined.
775 Results showed that high mean-to-nominal strength ratios exist for stainless steel frames due to the
776 considerably low nominal material properties specified for these materials, especially for austenitic and

777 ferritic grades. From the system strength probabilistic distributions, and in conjunction with First-Order
778 Reliability Method (FORM) techniques, system safety factors $\gamma_{M,s}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s
779 were derived for the direct design of stainless steel frames under gravity loads according to the
780 European, US and Australian design frameworks, considering a range of target system reliability indices
781 β_0 . The results suggested that a system safety factor of $\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15$ may be adopted for the Eurocode
782 framework to achieve a target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 3.8$, while resistance factors of $\phi_s = 0.95$ and
783 0.90 are appropriate for the US and Australian frameworks, respectively, for a target index of $\beta_0 = 3.0$.
784 These recommendations are based on the results obtained from reliability calibrations in this paper and
785 can be of assistance to specification committees in defining suitable values for $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s , although
786 the choice of target reliability indices ultimately rest with these committees and will affect the safety
787 and resistance factors. Further research to determine $\gamma_{M,s}$ and ϕ_s factors for stainless steel frames under
788 combined gravity and wind loads is underway.

789 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

790 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation
791 Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. 842395.

792 **REFERENCES**

- 793 [1] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1993-1-1. Eurocode 3: Design of Steel
794 Structures – Part 1-1: General Rules and Rules for Buildings. Final Document. Brussels, Belgium, 2019.
- 795 [2] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1993-1-4. Eurocode 3: Design of Steel
796 Structures – Part 1-4: General Rules. Supplementary Rules for Stainless Steels. Third draft. Brussels,
797 Belgium, 2020.
- 798 [3] AS/NZS 4100 Steel Structures. Standards Australia, Sydney, Australia, 2020.
- 799 [4] American Institute of Steel Construction (ANSI/AISC). AISC 360-16. Specification for Structural
800 Steel Buildings. Illinois, USA, 2016.
- 801 [5] Zhang H., Liu H., Ellingwood B.R. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliabilities of planar gravity steel
802 frames designed by the inelastic method in AISC 360-10. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)*
803 144(3):04018011, 2018.

804 [6] Zhang H., Shayan S., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Ellingwood B.R. System-based design of planar steel
805 frames, I: Reliability framework. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 123, 135–143, 2016.

806 [7] Zhang H., Shayan S., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Ellingwood B.R. System-based design of planar steel
807 frames, II: Reliability results and design recommendations. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*
808 123, 154–161, 2016.

809 [8] Liu W., Zhang H. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliability-based Direct Design Method for space
810 frames with cold-formed steel hollow sections. *Engineering Structures* 166, 79–92, 2018.

811 [9] Sena Cardoso F., Zhang H., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Yan S. Reliability calibrations for the design of
812 cold-formed steel portal frames by advanced analysis. *Engineering Structures* 182, 164–171, 2019.

813 [10] American Institute of Steel Construction (ANSI/AISC). AISC 370. Specification for Structural
814 Stainless Steel Buildings. Illinois, USA, 2021.

815 [11] Working Group 22 for Eurocode 3 CEN/TC 250/SC3/WG22. prEN 1993-1-14. Eurocode 3:
816 Design of steel structures – Part 1-14: Design assisted by finite element analysis. Brussels, Belgium.
817 *Under development.*

818 [12] Sena Cardoso F., Zhang H. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliability-based criteria for the design
819 of steel storage rack frames by advanced analysis: Part II – Reliability analysis and design applications.
820 *Thin-Walled Structures* 141, 725–739, 2019.

821 [13] Wang C., Zhang H., Rasmussen K.J.R., Reynolds J. and Yan S. Reliability-based limit state design
822 of support scaffolding systems. *Engineering Structures* 216, 110677, 2020.

823 [14] NewGeneSS, New Generation Design Methods for Stainless Steel Structures. Marie Skłodowska-
824 Curie Fellowship 2018, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation
825 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 842395.

826 [15] Baddoo N.R. Stainless steel in construction: A review of research, applications, challenges and
827 opportunities. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 64(11), 1199–1206, 2008.

828 [16] Cashell K.A. and Baddoo N.R. Ferritic stainless steels in structural applications. *Thin-Walled*
829 *Structures* 83, 169–181, 2014.

830 [17] Afshan S., Francis P., Baddoo N.R. and Gardner L. Reliability analysis of structural stainless steel
831 design provisions. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 114, 293–304, 2015.

- 832 [18] Gardner L. Stability and design of stainless steel structures – Review and outlook. *Thin-Walled*
833 *Structures* 141, 208–216, 2019.
- 834 [19] Walport F., Gardner L., Real E., Arrayago I. and Nethercot D.A. Effects of material nonlinearity
835 on the global analysis and stability of stainless steel frames. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*
836 152, 173–182, 2019.
- 837 [20] American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). SEI/ASCE 8. Specification for the Design of Cold-
838 Formed Stainless Steel Structural Members. Virginia, USA, 2021.
- 839 [21] American Iron and Steel Institute (AISI). AISI S100-16. North American Specification for the
840 Design of Cold-Formed Steel Structural Members. Illinois, USA, 2016.
- 841 [22] AS/NZS 4673 Cold-formed stainless steel structures. Standards Australia, Sydney, Australia,
842 2001.
- 843 [23] Henderson J.R. Design of steel portal frame buildings to Eurocode 3. SCI Publication P399. UK, 2015.
- 844 [24] Salter P.R., Malik A.S. and King C.M. Design of single-span steel portal frames to BS 5950-
845 1:2000. SCI Publication P252. UK, 2004.
- 846 [25] Gardner L. and Nethercot D.A. Numerical modelling of stainless steel structural components - A
847 consistent approach. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 130(10), 1586–1601, 2004.
- 848 [26] Packer J.A., Wardenier J., Kurobane Y., Dutta D. and Yeomans N. Design guide for rectangular
849 hollow section (RHS) joints under predominantly static loading. CIDECT Design Guide No. 3. Verlag
850 TÜV Rheinland GmbH, Köln, Germany, 1992.
- 851 [27] Wilkinson T. and Hancock G.J. Tests to examine plastic behaviour of knee joints in cold-formed
852 RHS. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 126(3), 297–305, 2000.
- 853 [28] Mang F., Steidl G. and Bucak O. Design of welded lattice joints and moment resisting knee joints
854 made of hollow sections. International Institute of Welding, Document XV-463-80. University of
855 Karlsruhe, Germany, 1980.
- 856 [29] Wardenier J. Hollow section joints. Delft University Press. Delft, The Netherlands, 1982.
- 857 [30] Arrayago I., González-de-León I., Real E. and Mirambell E. Tests on stainless steel frames. Part I:
858 Preliminary tests and experimental set-up. *Thin-Walled Structures* 157,107005, 2020.

859 [31] Arrayago I., González-de-León I., Real E. and Mirambell E. Tests on stainless steel frames. Part
860 II: Results and analysis. *Thin-Walled Structures* 157,107006, 2020.

861 [32] Arrayago I., Real E. and Gardner L. Description of stress–strain curves for stainless steel alloys.
862 *Materials and Design* 87, 540–552, 2015.

863 [33] Rasmussen K.J.R. Full-range stress–strain curves for stainless steel alloys. *Journal of*
864 *Constructional Steel Research* 59(1), 47–61, 2003.

865 [34] Steel Construction Institute (SCI). Design Manual for Structural Stainless Steel. Fourth Edition. UK, 2017.

866 [35] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). EN 10088-4. Stainless Steels Part 4: Technical
867 Delivery Conditions for Sheet/Plate and Strip of Corrosion Resisting Steels for Construction Purposes.
868 Brussels, Belgium, 2009.

869 [36] Rossi B., Afshan S. and Gardner L. Strength enhancements in cold-formed structural sections –
870 Part II: Predictive models. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 83, 189–196, 2013.

871 [37] Gardner L. and Cruise R.B. Modeling of residual stresses in structural stainless steel sections.
872 *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 135(1), 42–53, 2009.

873 [38] ABAQUS. version 6.10. Simulia, Dassault Systèmes, France, 2010.

874 [39] Arrayago I., Picci F., Mirambell E. and Real E. Interaction of bending and axial load for ferritic
875 stainless steel RHS columns. *Thin-Walled Structures* 91, 96–107, 2015.

876 [40] Huang Y. and Young B. Design of cold-formed lean duplex stainless steel members in combined
877 compression and bending. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 141(5): 04014138, 2015.

878 [41] Jandera M., Gardner L. and Machacek J. Residual stresses in cold-rolled stainless steel hollow
879 sections. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 64 (11), 1255–1263, 2008.

880 [42] Rasmussen K.J.R. and Hancock G.J. Design of cold-formed stainless steel tubular members. I:
881 Columns. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 119(8), 2349–2367, 1993.

882 [43] Arrayago I., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Real E. Statistical analysis of the material, geometrical and
883 imperfection characteristics of structural stainless steels and members. *Journal of Constructional Steel*
884 *Research* 175, 106378, 2020.

885 [44] Holický M., Retief J.V. and Sýkora M. Assessment of model uncertainties for structural resistance.
886 *Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics* 45, 188–197, 2016.

887 [45] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). EN 1990:2005. Eurocode: Basis of Structural
888 Design. Brussels, Belgium, 2005.

889 [46] Gulvanessian H. and Holicky M. Eurocodes: using reliability analysis to combine action effects.
890 *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers, Structures & Buildings* 158(SB4), 243–252, 2005.

891 [47] Joint Committee on Structural Safety (JCSS). Probabilistic Model Code, Zurich, Switzerland, 2001.

892 [48] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). EN 1991-1-1. Eurocode 1: Actions on structures
893 – Part 1-1: General actions. Densities, self-weight, imposed loads for buildings. Brussels, Belgium,
894 2002.

895 [49] American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). ASCE 7. Minimum design loads and associated
896 criteria for buildings and other structures. Virginia, USA, 2016.

897 [50] AS/NZS 1170.1. Structural design actions, Part 1: Permanent, imposed and other actions.
898 Standards Australia, Sydney, Australia, 2016.

899 [51] Ellingwood B.R., MacGregor J.G., Galambos T.V. and Cornell C.A. Probability based load
900 criteria: Load factors and load combinations. *Journal of Structural Division* 108(5), 978–997, 1982.

901 [52] Honfi D., A. Mårtensson A. and Thelandersson S. Reliability of beams according to Eurocodes in
902 serviceability limit state. *Engineering Structures* 35, 48–54, 2012.

903 [53] Holický M. Implementation of Eurocodes. Handbook 3: Action effects for buildings. Chapter I – Self-
904 weight and imposed loads on buildings. Leonardo da Vinci Pilot Project CZ/02/B/F/PP-134007, 2005.

905 [54] AS/NZS 1170.0 Structural design actions, Part 0: General principles. Standards Australia, Sydney,
906 Australia, 2002.

907 [55] Melchers R.E. Structural reliability analysis and prediction. John Wiley & Sons, 1999.

908 [56] Ziemian R.D., McGuire W. and Deierlein G.G. Inelastic limit states design. Part I: planar frame
909 studies. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 118(9), 2532–2549, 1992.

910 [57] MATLAB version 9.8.0 (R2020a). The MathWorks Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, 2020.

911 [58] Lefebvre M. Applied Probability and Statistics. Springer Science+Business Media LLC, 2006.

912 [59] McAllister T.P., Wang N. and Ellingwood B.R. Risk-informed mean recurrence intervals for
913 updated wind maps in ASCE 7-16. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 144(5):06018001, 2018.

- 914 [60] Ellingwood B.R. Acceptable risk bases for design of structures. *Progress in Structural Engineering*
915 *and Materials* 3(2), 170–179, 2001.
- 916 [61] Ellingwood B.R. LRFD: implementing structural reliability in professional practice. *Engineering*
917 *Structures* 22, 106–15, 2000.
- 918 [62] Ad Hoc Group for Eurocode 0 CEN/TC 250/SC10. Reliability Technical Report for the reliability
919 background of Eurocodes. *Draft document*, August 2020.
- 920 [63] Vrouwenvelder A.C.W.M. and Siemes A.J.M. Probabilistic calibration procedure for the derivation
921 of partial safety factors for the Netherlands building codes. *HERON* 32 (4), 9–31, 1987.
- 922 [64] Galambos T.V., Ellingwood B.R., MacGregor J.G. and Cornell C.A. Probability Based Load
923 Criteria: Assessment of Current Design Practice. *Journal of the Structural Division (ASCE)* 108(5),
924 959–977, 1982.
- 925 [65] Ellingwood B.R. and Tekie P.B. Wind load statistics for probability-based structural design.
926 *Journal of Structural Engineering* 125(4), 453–463, 1999.

FIGURES

Figure 1. General layout of investigated frames.

Figure 2. Constitutive moment-rotation model adopted for connection behaviour.

Figure 3. Overall view of developed FE model and definition of vertical loading and joints.

Figure 4. Comparison of FE and experimental load-deflection and load-displacement curves.

Figure 5. Histograms for system strength of stainless steel frames under gravity loads.

Figure 6. $\beta - \gamma_{M,s}$ curves for stainless steel frames under gravity loads in the Eurocode framework for different Q_k/G_k ratios.

Figure 7. $\beta - \phi_s$ curves for stainless steel frames under gravity loads in the US framework for different L_n/D_n ratios.

Figure 8. $\beta - \phi_s$ curves for stainless steel frames under gravity loads in the Australian framework for different Q_n/G_n ratios.

Figure 9. Comparison of $\beta - \gamma_{M,s}$ and $\beta - 1/\phi_s$ curves for stainless steel frames under gravity loads for $Q_k/G_k = 2$, $L_n/D_n = 2$ or $Q_n/G_n = 2$.

TABLES

Table 1. Key parameters for nominal stainless steel frames.

Variable group	Variable	Austenitic stainless steel		Duplex stainless steel		Ferritic stainless steel	
		Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6
Overall frame geometry	s [m]	8.0	10.0	8.0	12.0	8.0	11.0
	H ₁ [m]	4.8	6.4	4.8	6.6	4.8	6.5
	H ₂ [m]	6.0	7.0	6.0	7.4	6.0	7.2
Cross-section definition	H [mm]	150	250	150	250	150	250
	B [mm]	100	150	100	150	100	150
	t [mm]	4	4	4	4	4	4
Initial geometric imperfections	Frame imp. ϕ [-]	1/200 ⁺ 1/500*					
	Member imp. e_0 [mm]	L/1000	L/1000	L/1000	L/1000	L/1000	L/1000
	Local imp. w_0 [mm]	0.017	0.040	0.030	0.072	0.017	0.043
Joint behaviour at bases	K _{1,base} [kNm/rad]	4000	Pinned	4000	Pinned	4000	Pinned
	K _{2,base} [kNm/rad]	400	-	400	-	400	-
	M _{1,base} [kNm]	26.3	-	41.4	-	27.0	-
	M _{2,base} [kNm]	40.4	-	63.4	-	41.4	-
Joint behaviour at eaves	K _{1,eave} [kNm/rad]	6400	7000	6400	9000	6400	8000
	K _{2,eave} [kNm/rad]	640	700	640	900	640	800
	M _{1,eave} [kNm]	23.9	50.0	37.6	86.4	24.6	51.5
	M _{2,eave} [kNm]	37.4	78.2	58.7	105.4	38.4	80.5
Joint behaviour at apex	K _{1,apex} [kNm/rad]	6600	7500	6600	9500	6600	8500
	K _{2,apex} [kNm/rad]	660	750	660	950	660	850
	M _{1,apex} [kNm]	25.4	53.1	39.9	91.8	26.1	54.8
	M _{2,apex} [kNm]	37.4	78.2	58.7	105.4	38.4	80.5

⁺: Frame imperfection corresponding to prEN 1993-1-1 [1] and prEN 1993-1-14 [11].

*: Frame imperfection corresponding to AS/NZS 4100 [3], AISC 360 [4] or AISC 370 [10].

Table 2. Nominal material parameters for frames in the Eurocode framework [2,35].

Variable	Austenitic EN 1.4301		Duplex EN 1.4462		Ferritic EN 1.4003	
	Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6
E [MPa]	200000	200000	200000	200000	200000	200000
f _y [MPa]	230	230	500	500	280	280
f _{y,enh} [MPa]	297	279	507	503	299	300
n [-]	7	7	8	8	14	14
f _u [MPa]	550	550	700	700	450	450
ε _u [mm/mm]	0.46	0.49	0.28	0.28	0.20	0.20
m [-]	2.5	2.4	3.0	3.0	2.9	2.9

Table 3. Nominal material parameters for frames in the US framework [20].

Variable	Austenitic ASTM 304		Duplex ASTM 2205		Ferritic ASTM UNS S40977	
	Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6
E [MPa]	193000	193000	200000	200000	200000	200000
f_y [MPa]	205	205	450	450	280*	280*
$f_{y,enh}$ [MPa]	271	254	465	454	299	296
n [-]	7	7	8	8	14	14
f_u [MPa]	515	515	655	655	435*	435*
ϵ_u [mm/mm]	0.47	0.51	0.29	0.31	0.19	0.19
m [-]	2.5	2.4	3.0	2.9	2.9	2.9

*: Nominal material parameters correspond to the AS/NZS 4673 [22] Specification.

Table 4. Nominal material parameters for frames in the Australian framework [22].

Variable	Austenitic ASTM 304		Duplex ASTM 2205		Ferritic ASTM UNS S40977	
	Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4	Frame 5	Frame 6
E [MPa]	195000	195000	200000*	200000*	195000	195000
f_y [MPa]	205	205	450*	450*	280	280
$f_{y,enh}$ [MPa]	273	255	465	454	299	296
n [-]	7.5	7.5	8*	8*	9	9
f_u [MPa]	520	520	655*	655*	435	435
ϵ_u [mm/mm]	0.48	0.51	0.29	0.31	0.19	0.19
m [-]	2.5	2.4	3.0	2.9	2.9	2.9

*: Nominal material parameters correspond to the ASCE 8 [20] Specification.

Table 5. Comparison of FE and experimental results.

Specimen	$F_{v,FE}/F_{v,exp}$	$d_{v,FE}/d_{v,exp}$	$F_{h,FE}/F_{h,exp}$	$d_{h,FE}/d_{h,exp}$
Specimen 1	1.00	1.01	1.00	1.02
Specimen 2	1.00	1.02	1.00	0.99
Specimen 3	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.05
Specimen 4	1.00	1.03	1.00	1.01
Mean	1.00	1.01	1.00	1.02
COV	0.000	0.017	0.000	0.024

Table 6. Statistics of random variables defining frame strength.

Random variable type	Random variable	Mean	St. Deviation	COV	Statistical distribution	Reference
Cross-section definition	H [mm]	$1.002 \cdot H_n$	$0.012 \cdot H_n$	0.012	Normal	
	B [mm]	$1.002 \cdot B_n$	$0.010 \cdot B_n$	0.010	Normal	[43]
	t [mm]	$0.974 \cdot t_n$	$0.028 \cdot t_n$	0.029	Normal	
Initial geometric imperfections	Frame imp. ϕ [-]	0.0	1/610	-	Normal	[9]
	Member imp. e_0 [mm]	L/3232	L/5369	0.602	Log-normal	[43]
	Local imp. γ_2 [-]	0.041	0.026	0.636	Log-normal	[43]
Residual stresses	Scale Factor Y	0.875	0.161	0.184	Normal	[43]
Joint behaviour	K_1 [kNm/rad]	$1.0 \cdot K_{1,n}$	$0.30 \cdot K_{1,n}$	0.300	Log-normal	
	K_2 [kNm/rad]	$1.0 \cdot K_{2,n}$	$0.15 \cdot K_{2,n}$	0.150	Log-normal	[9]
	M_1 [kNm]	$1.0 \cdot M_{1,n}$	$0.10 \cdot M_{1,n}$	0.100	Log-normal	
	M_2 [kNm]	$1.0 \cdot M_{2,n}$	$0.15 \cdot M_{2,n}$	0.150	Log-normal	
Model uncertainty	θ or γ_{FE}	1.0	0.05	0.05	Log-normal	[46,47]

Note: the subscript n represents the nominal value and L is the length of the member.

Table 7. Statistics of material random variables for cold-formed stainless steel alloys [43].

Alloy family	Random variable	Mean	St. Deviation	COV	Statistical distribution
Austenitic cold-formed	E [MPa]	193084	11039	0.057	Normal
	f_y	$1.30 \cdot f_{y,enh,n}$	$0.195 \cdot f_{y,enh,n}$	0.150	Log-normal
	n [-]	6.0	2.1	0.342	Log-normal
	f_u	$1.10 \cdot f_{u,n}$	$0.11 \cdot f_{u,n}$	0.100	Log-normal
	ϵ_u [mm/mm]	0.39	0.15	0.373	Normal
	m [-]	3.1	1.3	0.426	Log-normal
Duplex cold-formed	E [MPa]	205025	8700	0.042	Normal
	f_y	$1.15 \cdot f_{y,enh,n}$	$0.173 \cdot f_{y,enh,n}$	0.150	Log-normal
	n [-]	6.3	2.1	0.332	Log-normal
	f_u	$1.10 \cdot f_{u,n}$	$0.11 \cdot f_{u,n}$	0.100	Log-normal
	ϵ_u [mm/mm]	0.24	0.14	0.579	Normal
	m [-]	4.2	1.9	0.462	Log-normal
Ferritic cold-formed	E [MPa]	198572	15582	0.078	Normal
	f_y	$1.30 \cdot f_{y,enh,n}$	$0.195 \cdot f_{y,enh,n}$	0.150	Log-normal
	n [-]	10.1	5.4	0.536	Log-normal
	f_u	$1.10 \cdot f_{u,n}$	$0.11 \cdot f_{u,n}$	0.100	Log-normal
	ϵ_u [mm/mm]	0.13	0.11	0.852	Normal
	m [-]	3.5	2.2	0.619	Log-normal

Table 8. Statistics of gravity loads for different design frameworks.

Design framework	Load case	Mean	COV	Statistical distribution
Eurocode framework	Permanent load G	$1.0 \cdot G_k$	0.10	Normal
	Imposed variable load Q	$0.8 \cdot Q_k$	0.25	Extreme Type I
US framework	Dead load D	$1.05 \cdot D_n$	0.10	Normal
	Imposed live load L	$1.0 \cdot L_n$	0.25	Extreme Type I
Australian framework	Dead load G	$1.05 \cdot G_n$	0.10	Normal
	Imposed live load Q	$1.0 \cdot Q_n$	0.25	Extreme Type I

Table 9. Summary of statistics for system strength of stainless steel frames under gravity loads.

Frame	Nominal EN resistance $R_{k,EN}$ [kN]	Nominal US resistance $R_{n,US}$ [kN]	Nominal AU resistance $R_{n,AU}$ [kN]	Mean system strength R_m [kN]	COV of system strength	$R_m/R_{k,EN}$	$R_m/R_{n,US}$	$R_m/R_{n,AU}$	Statistical distribution
Frame 1	66.3	60.8	60.9	83.5	0.117	1.26	1.37	1.37	Log-normal
Frame 2	101.9	94.4	95.6	120.5	0.113	1.18	1.28	1.26	Log-normal
Frame 3	106.1	98.6	98.6	124.8	0.089	1.18	1.27	1.27	Log-normal
Frame 4	140.7	131.4	131.4	166.5	0.114	1.18	1.27	1.27	Log-normal
Frame 5	66.6	66.2	66.5	83.2	0.112	1.25	1.26	1.25	Log-normal
Frame 6	101.0	102.4	101.0	120.5	0.111	1.19	1.18	1.19	Log-normal

Table 10. Required system safety factors $\gamma_{M,S}$ and system resistance factors ϕ_s for stainless steel frames under gravity loads
(for $Q_k/G_k = 2$, $L_n/D_n = 2$ or $Q_n/G_n = 2$) for different target reliability indices β_0 and different design frameworks.

Frame	Eurocode framework			US framework		Australian framework	
	Reliability index β_0	Required system safety factor $\gamma_{M,S}$	$1/\gamma_{M,S} \sim \phi_s$	Required system resistance factor ϕ_s	$1/\phi_s \sim \gamma_{M,S}$	Required system resistance factor ϕ_s	$1/\phi_s \sim \gamma_{M,S}$
Frame 1	3.8	1.10	0.91	0.83	1.21	0.79	1.27
	3.3	0.97	1.03	0.94	1.06	0.90	1.11
	3.0	0.90	1.11	1.02	0.98	0.97	1.03
	2.5	0.79	1.26	1.16	0.86	1.11	0.90
Frame 2	3.8	1.17	0.86	0.77	1.29	0.73	1.37
	3.3	1.03	0.97	0.88	1.13	0.83	1.20
	3.0	0.95	1.05	0.95	1.05	0.90	1.11
	2.5	0.84	1.19	1.08	0.92	1.02	0.98
Frame 3	3.8	1.13	0.89	0.80	1.25	0.76	1.31
	3.3	1.00	1.00	0.91	1.10	0.86	1.16
	3.0	0.93	1.08	0.98	1.02	0.93	1.07
	2.5	0.82	1.21	1.11	0.90	1.06	0.95
Frame 4	3.8	1.17	0.86	0.77	1.30	0.73	1.37
	3.3	1.03	0.97	0.88	1.14	0.84	1.20
	3.0	0.95	1.05	0.95	1.06	0.90	1.11
	2.5	0.84	1.19	1.08	0.93	1.03	0.97
Frame 5	3.8	1.10	0.91	0.76	1.31	0.73	1.38
	3.3	0.97	1.03	0.87	1.15	0.83	1.21
	3.0	0.90	1.11	0.94	1.06	0.89	1.12
	2.5	0.80	1.26	1.07	0.94	1.02	0.98
Frame 6	3.8	1.15	0.87	0.72	1.40	0.69	1.44
	3.3	1.02	0.98	0.82	1.22	0.79	1.27
	3.0	0.94	1.06	0.88	1.13	0.85	1.17
	2.5	0.83	1.20	1.00	1.00	0.97	1.03